

$8T - \hat{T}$ as a Sum of Accelerations

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting in which $8T$ is built upon, i.e. Lorentz manifold and calculus of variation, author will present a new form of the Hamiltonian operator of a varying manifold. The new form is based upon a decomposition of the kinetic energy term, which will allow analysis of each area of extremum curvature by itself.

Introduction

The main equation of the $8T$ is describing the variation of a Lorentz manifold, which according to the second equation (1.1) can be expressed as being part of a manifold packet. Such a theoretical construction manifested in one equation, is able to provide an answer to three major questions at the heart of major cosmology. The flatness puzzle, the "dark energy" puzzle and the "dark matter" puzzle by (1.2).

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_m - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_n = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The subject matter of this paper is the following question, can we represent the Hamiltonian of the manifold as a sum of spikes arbitrary spikes all across the matrix. The author will argue that the answer is positive. First, let us represent the Hamiltonian of the system as presented in pages 205-206 within the 8T thesis:

$$\begin{aligned}
 U &= \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{1=1}^M \delta g_i \\
 &\sum_{1=1}^M \delta g_i < \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \\
 \hat{H} &= \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{1=1}^M \delta g_i = \hat{T} + \hat{U}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.3}$$

The potential energy is arbitrary variation clusters which vanish into matter, than Bosonic ripples propagating within them, that is vanishing spikes and non-vanishing curvature spikes. The kinetic energy is given by the Ricci flow equivalent to the acceleration in (1). Now to make the Hamiltonian more accurate it is possible to decompose the kinetic term:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} = \sum_{\phi=1}^K \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} \right)_{\phi} \tag{1.4}$$

Such an operation would allow us to regard the kinetic the term as the sum of acceleration of distinct galaxies. As new areas of extremum curvature are being created, $K \rightarrow \infty$ and energy, as previously mentioned is not conserved as the Hamiltonian term is a subject to constant variance, which is increase. The increase does not interfere with the stationarity of the manifold as matter is appearing in a way that does not allow curvature to manifest itself. There could be additional uses for the kinetic term decomposition such as a collusion between two galaxies, which now mean that there is new area of extremum curvature, with new rate of acceleration. The new rate of acceleration is the summation of the kinetic terms of each distinct galaxies:

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} \right)_{\phi=1} + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} \right)_{\phi=2} = \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} \right)_{\phi=1+2}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad's Theory